

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on the extraction procedure scale up of the selected extracts and on the chromatographic methodology for the extract's standardization

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry

Flagship project VINO RM4 - Don't waste the waste

DELIVERABLE D4.4

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Herein the evaluation of the scalability of the extraction procedures previously optimized for pruning residues of *Vitis vinifera* and *Olea europea* (see deliverables D 4.1 and D 4.1B, respectively) was evaluated. Chromatographic methodology already developed for *Vitis vinifera* pruning wood extracts (see deliverable D 4.2) was suitable for extract's standardization. Extract derived from pruning residues of *Olea europea* was successfully analyzed applying chromatographic conditions from literature.

A) Material and Methods

In this section chemicals (e.g. standards and solvents), instruments and methodologies used (e.g. for HPLC-UV analysis, MAE procedures, DPPH, assay) are reported.

Plant material

Vitis vinifera

One-year-old lignified shoots (= canes) of *Vitis vinifera* cv Syrah, were collected from 16-year-old vines in the collection vineyard of the University of Turin (DISAFA vineyard; 45 30530 0 N, 7350320 0 E) located in Grugliasco (TO), Italy, on the 2nd of February 2023. The DISAFA vineyard, planted in 2008, has a density of 4400 vines/ha and is situated 293 m above sea level in a flat area. Grapevines are vertical shoot positioned and trained in the Guyot pruning system.

Olea europea

One-year-old lignified shoots of *Olea europaea* L. cultivar Matosso were collected from a 5-year-old plant at the "VALENTINI GERMANO" Ca' Albertini 2-Frazione Pizzofreddo - Santa Maria della Versa, Pavia.

For both *Vitis vinifera* and *Olea europea*, after collection, the plant material was cleaned, cut, and left to dry in a ventilated oven at 35°C until it reached a constant weight, and then stored in a dark, dry place. Before extraction, the plant material was ground finely

Chemical

Formic acid, 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), HPLC grade Acetonitrile and Methanol were supplied by Merck-Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). Analytical grade ethanol was supplied by PanReac (Barcelona, Spain).

Instruments and apparatus

Plant material was ground using a Blade-mill (A10 IKA-Werke GmbH & Co., Staufen, Germany). MAE extractions were carried out on both a microwave mono-mode oven (Discover® Lab-Mate instrument, CEM Corporate, Buck-ingham, UK) equipped with a power and temperature controller, and a microwave multi-mode oven (MARSX system, CEM Corporate, Buckingham, UK). Sample solvent removal was carried out using a Heidolph Laborota 4,000 instrument (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co., Schwabach, Germany) and a Smart Evaporator C1 (Stepbio, Bologna, Italy).

UHPLC analyses were performed on a Jasco UHPLC-UV/PAD system (Jasco Europe, Cremella, Italy) equipped with a quaternary pump model PU-4180, autosampler model AS-4050 with a 5 µL loop, column thermostatic compartment model CO-4065; UV-Vis photodiode array detector (PAD) model MD-4010 with a semi-micro cell (Jasco 2023), ChromNAV software (version 2.04.03).

C

Microwave-assisted solvent extraction (MAE)

Vitis vinifera

MAE extraction was carried out using pure ethanol as extraction solvent using both a microwave mono-mode oven (Discover® Lab-Mate instrument, CEM Corporate, Buck-ingham, UK) and a microwave multi-mode oven (MARSX system, CEM Corporate, Buckingham, UK), for evaluating method scalability. Experimental conditions were set as follows:

microwave mono-mode oven

one 5-minute microwave cycle at 80°C (ramp time of 2 min), MW power of 50 Watts, drug/solvent ratio of 20% (400 mg of the matrix extracted with 2 mL of solvent).

microwave multi-mode oven

one 5-minute microwave cycle at 80°C (ramp time of 2 min), MW power 320W, drug/solvent ratio of 20% (60g of the matrix extracted with 300 mL of solvent)

Olea europea

MAE extraction was carried out using 80:20 ethanol/water as extraction solvent using both a microwave mono-mode oven (Discover® Lab-Mate instrument, CEM Corporate, Buck-ingham, UK) and a microwave multi-mode oven (MARSX system, CEM Corporate, Buckingham, UK), for evaluating method scalability. Experimental conditions were set as follows:

microwave mono-mode oven: one 5-minute microwave cycle at 40°C (ramp time of 2 min), power of 25 W, 1:50 plant material-to-solvent ratio (e.g. 250 mg of plant material extracted using 12.5 mL of solvent)

microwave multi-mode oven: one 5-minute microwave cycle at 40°C (ramp time of 2 min), power of power of 320 W, 1:50 plant material-to-solvent ratio (e.g. 6 g of plant material extracted using 300 mL of solvent)

For both *Vitis vinifera* and *Olea europea*, after extraction the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, filtered through vacuum filtration and finally solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure.

HPLC-UV analysis

Vitis vinifera

Extracts from *Vitis vinifera* pruning residues were analyzed according to the method previously developed (see Deliverable D 4.2). Briefly, UHPLC analysis were performed using the Purospher® STAR RP-18 endcapped column (2.1 mm ID x 100 mm, particle size 3 µm) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). The mobile phase consisted of water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (solvent A) and acetonitrile containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (solvent B). The elution was in gradient mode starting from 5% to 40% of B in 4 min, from 40% to 50% of B in 9 min, up to 80% of B in 7 min followed by an isocratic elution phase for 5 min. The column was reconditioned by eluting from 80% of B to 5% of B in 0.1 min and with a final 15 min isocratic elution at the initial conditions (5% of B).). The analyses were performed at 25°C and at a flow rate of 0.2 mL min⁻¹. The injection volume was 1 µL. The quantitation of (E)-resveratrol and (E)-ε-viniferin was performed at 306nm applying the external standard method (see Deliverable D 4.2)

Olea europea

Extracts from *Olea europaea* were analyzed according to Mir-Cerdà et al. using the Kinetex C18 column (4.6 mm ID x 150 mm, particle size 2.6 µm) (Phenomenex®, Torrance, California)¹. The mobile phase consisted of water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B). The elution was in gradient mode as follows: isocratic elution at 3% B for 3 min, from 3% to 30% of B in 18 min, from 30% to 65% of B in 5 min, up to 90% of B in 2 min. The column was reconditioned by eluting from 90% of B to 3% of B in 3 min, followed by a final isocratic elution at the initial conditions (3% of B) for 7 min. The analyses were performed at 25°C and at a flow rate of 0.7 mL min⁻¹. The injection volume of each sample was 3 µL. The UV-visible absorbance was recorded from 190 to 600 nm, and the quantification of oleuropein was performed at 230 nm applying the external standard method (see Deliverable D 4.1B).

Single-dose DPPH assay

After chlorophyll removal,² extracts from *Olea europea* pruning residues were tested by the DPPH assay using a multi-well plate, according to Brand-Williams et al., with slight modifications.³ Briefly, for each extract a stock solution was prepared at a concentration of 0.4

¹ Mir-Cerdà, A. et al. 'Olive Tree Leaves as a Great Source of Phenolic Compounds: Comprehensive Profiling of NaDES Extracts. *Food Chemistry* **2024**, 456:140042. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2024.140042.

² Fossati A et al. A practical and easy-to-scale protocol for removing chlorophylls from leaf extracts. *Appl Plant Sci.* 2025;13

³ Brand-Williams, W. et al. Use of a Free Radical Method to Evaluate Antioxidant Activity. *LWT - Food Science and Technology* **1995**, 28, 25–30, doi:10.1016/S0023-6438(95)80008-5.

mg mL⁻¹ in methanol. Then sample, blank and control solutions were prepared as follows: for sample solution 10 μ L of the extract stock solution were mixed with 190 μ L of DPPH methanolic solution (0.15 mM); for blank solution 190 μ L of methanol were mixed with 10 μ L of the extract stock solution; for control solution 190 μ L of DPPH methanolic solution (0.15 mM) were mixed with 10 μ L of methanol. The plate was incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes, and then the absorbance was measured at 515 nm using a microplate reader. The percentage of free radical scavenging activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\%FRS = 100 \times \frac{A_{ctrl} - (A_{sample} - A_{blank})}{A_{ctrl}}$$

Where

% FRS is the free radical scavenging activity percent, A_{ctrl} is the absorbance of the control, A_{sample} is the raw data reading of the sample and A_{blank} is the absorbance of the blank.

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel for Windows 365 MSO (Version 18.2002.1101.0), CAT (Chemometric Agile Tool, by Leardi, C. Melzi, G. Polotti), freely downloadable from <http://gruppochemiometria.it/index.php/software>, developed in R for Microsoft Windows (version 3.2.3, Copyright 2014) [66] and GraphPad Prism 8.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). Data are expressed as mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) of the mean. The Shapiro–Wilk and Bartlett Tests were used to establish the normality of the parameters. Then, population mean values comparisons were carried out using a one-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Statistical significance was evaluated at a 95% confidence interval, and the differences were considered statistically significant for $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***)

B) Scalability evaluation of extraction method

In this section the evaluation of the scalability of the MAE method for both *Vitis vinifera* and *Olea europea* pruning residues is described and discussed.

Vitis vinifera

The scalability of the optimized MAE extraction conditions previously identified (100% ethanol, one 5-minute microwave cycle at 80°C, drug/solvent ratio of 20%, see deliverable D 4.1) was investigated. To this purpose, the optimal parameters were applied to approximately 60 g of the pruning wood matrix in triplicate using a multimodal mw-oven as described in the experimental section. For comparative purposes, 400 mg of the wood matrix were also extracted in triplicate following the optimized conditions, operating on the same batch used for the 60 g-scale extraction. Results summarized in Table 1 clearly indicate that the change of scale and type of

mw-oven did not affect the extraction efficiency of the method, the amount of both metabolites being statistically unvaried between the two scales (two tails t-Test). With a view to large-scale application, recent advances in the microwave apparatus led to the development of a microwave extractor suitable for processing kilos of biomass. This, associated with the low extraction time of our method, would allow to process a high amount of biomass, thus overcoming scalability issues usually associated with MAE.

Table 1 Evaluation of method scalability for *Vitis vinifera* pruning wood extraction

Amount of matrix (pruning wood)	(E)-Resveratrol amount* (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	(E)-ε-Viniferin amount* (mg g ⁻¹ DW)
~ 400 mg	0.77 ± 0.03	1.40 ± 0.06
~ 60 g	0.81 ± 0.01	1.36 ± 0.02

*Metabolites quantified by UHPLC-UV/PAD calibration curves in the crude extract. Results are expressed as mean of three experiments ± SD

Olea europea

The scalability of the optimized MAE extraction conditions previously identified (80:20 ethanol/water, single 5-minute microwave cycle at 40°C, 1:50 solid-to-solvent ratio, see deliverable D 4.1B) was investigated. To this purpose, the optimal parameters were applied to approximately 6 g of each matrix (branches, leaves, and unprocessed pruning waste as a mixture of leaves and branches) in triplicate using a multimodal microwave oven, as detailed in the experimental section. For comparative purposes, 0.25 g of each matrix were also extracted in triplicate following the optimized conditions, operating on the same batch used for the 6 g-scale extraction. Notably, comparable extraction efficiency was achieved at both 0.25 g and 6 g scales (24-fold scale-up), being either extraction yields or oleuropein recovery statistically unvaried within the same biomass (two tails t-Test). Similarly, FRS potential also remained statistically equivalent between scales (two tails t-Test), thus demonstrating an excellent reproducibility of the scale-up process for all the biomass considered (Table 1). Overall, based on the results reported above, none of the biomass considered exhibited scale-dependent behavior.

Table 1. Evaluation of method scalability for *Olea europea* pruning residue extraction

Branches			
Amount of matrix	Extraction yield (% w/w)	Oleuropein amount* (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	FRS (%)

0.25 g	19.7 ± 1.7	37.1 ± 4.5	76.5 ± 5.5
6 g	21.5 ± 1.7	29.8 ± 7.4	69.9 ± 2.5
Leaves			
Amount of matrix	Extraction yield (% w/w)	Oleuropein amount* (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	FRS (%)
0.25 g	40.0 ± 0.4	96.4 ± 11.6	84.0 ± 5.5
6 g-	43.2 ± 1.3	108.6 ± 10.0	82.9 ± 2.8
Unprocessed Pruning waste			
Amount of matrix	Extraction yield (% w/w)	Oleuropein amount* (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	FRS (%)
0.25 g-	25.1 ± 2.9	47.6 ± 9.5	92.2 ± 6.0
6 g-	27.0 ± 1.1	51.7 ± 4.7	82.3 ± 1.7

*Metabolite quantified by UHPLC-UV/PAD calibration curves in the extract Results are reported as mean ± SD of three experiments